

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 3, No. 2; February 28, 1997

Dear Readers:

This issue again lives up to the expectations of J.UCS, I feel: it consists of three papers from rather different fields, each interesting in its own way.

I do hope you will enjoy this issue. Please, keep supporting J.UCS by mentioning it to colleagues, both from a point of view as valuable resource, and as potential journal for publication.

Observe that J.UCS, from the beginning onward, has offered readers and authors the possibility to annotate papers, e.g. adding remarks when they publish new results that improve earlier ones. This feature has not been used extensively.

We intend to make the contributions of such remarks still easier in the future by creating a closed user group: if you belong to it (you have to sign up!) then you can add comments to a paper immediately, and all comments will be collected in a list that is sorted in reverse order by date. If you have any remarks or suggestions concerning this feature please let me know: we want to incorporate it the first time in the May issue: it will work retroactively for all of J.UCS.

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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